

Utilizing Authentic Materials are Important to Promote Good Habits of Reading among High School Students

K. GAYITHRI DEVI Ph.D. Scholar, Prof. P. Hari Padma Rani, Research Supervisor
Department of English Sri Padmavathi Mahila Vishva Vidhyalayam Tirupathi

Abstract:- “Reading is important. If you know how to read, then the whole world opens up to you”. – Barack Obama.

Reading is an important mode of comprehension and acquiring knowledge. The students should possess a sound training in reading mother tongue when they begin reading the second language. This thought can lead the students to read well and read with understanding. If the students can read well, they can get enjoyment and pleasure out of the language.

To develop good habits of reading among students, the authentic material is the most important. It takes part in the intellectual, psychological and communal evolution of a person. This can generate the innovative thoughts, can create a pleasant atmosphere and an interest in reading other materials.

The sources of authentic materials that can be used in the class room is infinite, but the most common are newspapers, magazines, T.V. programmes, movies, songs and literature. One of the most useful sources is the internet.

Keywords:- Authentic Materials, intellectual, psychological, communal evolution, Innovative.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to *M.L.Tickoo...* Good reading habits promote self- education which helps in the modification of the personality. We must form of hobby of reading. Reading is a process of looking at written or printed symbol and translating it into an appropriate written or printed symbol and translating it into an appropriate sound.

A mature reader uses two types of knowledge to gain meaning from the printed word. The first is the Knowledge of Language Systems (KOLS); the sounds and letters of the alphabet, words and their parts, sentences and their constituents. In technical language KOLS comprises knowledge related to sounds (Phonology), words (Lexis) and such aspects as spelling and order of letters/words (Morphosyntactic Knowledge).

The second type of Knowledge is Of the World (KOW) and in particular of the subject being read. A mature reader normally approaches the text with some expectation or understanding of what the author may have to say; as a result, he generally finds the act of reading more rewarding

than a reader without similar background knowledge or expectations.

II. DEFINITIONS

- “ Reading is a process of recognizing printed or written symbols involving such habits as accuracy in recognizing the words and phrases and sentences “.
- “ Reading means understanding what the writer has said in a text”.
- “It means extracting the required information ”.
- “ Reading makes a full man conversation a complete man”.
- “ Reading is form of experience”.- W.S. Gray.

III. AUTHENTIC MATERIALS

- According to the *Dictionnaire de Didactique des Langues, Galisson and Coste (1976) and Gallien (1998)*, “authentic” does not necessarily mean natural or spontaneous. However, authentic materials are “originally produced for a real communicative, informative or linguistic function” as contrary to those produced for use in the classroom specially (p. 156).
- On the other hand, *Swaffar (1985)* knows authentic text as a text designed for a group of language learners.
- *Breen (1985)* provides an example: a poem from a textbook, by *Miroslav Holub* (poet, 1923 – 1998) along with a short story and states that the poem is a piece of authentic material and realizes as an illustration of lexical items or linguistic structures whereas the story can give authentic feelings to the learners.
- According to *Wu (2008)*, the first person who proposed a clear definition of “authentic documents “is *Daniel Coste (1970)*. He defines them as: “the documents produced by native speakers for native speakers “(*Gallien, 1998*).
- *Duda, Esch & Laurens, (1972)* tried to define them regarding those characteristics that they do not have. They know authentic documents, as “foreign-language documents whose original purpose is not the teaching of that language “(*Gallien, 1998, p.156*).
- *Breen (1985)* is the first researcher who divided authenticity into four types:
 - Authenticity of the text, which can be used as input data for our learners.
 - Authenticity of the learners’ own interpretations of such texts.
 - Authenticity of tasks conducive to language learning.
 - Authenticity of the actual social situation of the language classroom (p.61).

IV. DEFINITION OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS

Al-Azri and Al-Rashdi (2014) cite *Martinez* (2002) in their article, which emphasizes to prepare for native speakers rather than teaching purposes. They also refer to *Kilickaya* (2004) who states the importance of real language of community where the language is used.

Authentic texts are explained with “designed for native speakers” and “designed not for language students” by *Harmer* (1991). Today this is not important who and for whom the materials are designed, but the matter of consideration is that whether the language is real in nature, and is it used for creating a genuine context in the classroom. Moreover, the definition of authentic materials is not based on ‘designed for native speakers by native speakers.

V. THE USE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN READING

Reading means different things to different people. For some it is recognizing written words, while for others it is an opportunity to learn pronunciation and practice speaking. However reading always has a purpose. It is something that we do every day. It is an integral part of our daily lives, taken very much for granted and generally assumed to be something that everyone can do.

Non- English Medium learner is exposed to language only in the English classroom and English reader is the source of material. Therefore authentic material can help them read wherever there is an opportunity. The learners benefit from the exposure to real language being used in a real context.

A. Objectives:

- It helps the learners to equip themselves to develop the reading skills.
- It raises awareness about reading.
- It enables the learners create an interest in reading.
- It helps the learners to acquire the skills and techniques that makes reading enjoyable.
- It makes the learners to become self -reliant.
- It makes the learners to become efficient readers.

B. Learning Outcomes:

- The readers/learners acquire the skill and techniques of reading.
- The learners take up appropriate authentic material to get reading enjoyable.
- The learner uses authentic material to develop reading skills.

VI. WHAT IS AUTHENTIC READING MATERIAL?

Authentic texts have been defined as” real life texts, not written for pedagogic purpose” (*Wallac* 1992 :145). They are therefore written for native speakers and contain “real” Language. They are: materials that have been produced to fulfill some social purpose in the language community *Peacock* (1997) in contrast to non -authentic

texts that are especially designed for language learning purposes.

The sources of authentic materials that can be used in the classroom are infinite, but the most common are newspapers, magazines, T.V. programs, movies, songs and literature. One of the most useful sources is the Internet.

Authentic materials should be the kind of material that readers will need and want to be able to read, when travelling, studying abroad, or using the language in other contexts outside the classroom.

Other Authentic materials we come across are....

- Tooth brush cover
- Tooth paste cover
- Chocolate paper
- Biscuit Wrapper
- Healthy drinks like Horlicks, Boost etc.
- Recipes, menu cards
- Food Wrappers, tins
- Instructions on medicine bottles, tablet strips
- Cold drink packs
- Posters, Banners, captions.
- Road maps
- Placards at the matches
- Instruction to play video games.
- Cartoons
- Letters, telegrams, e-mails, notes weather.

VII. WHY DO WE NEED AUTHENTIC READING MATERIAL?

Reading can have three main purposes for survival, for learning, or for pleasure.

Reading for survival is considered to be in response to our environment and to find out information which can include street signs, advertisement and time table.

“Authentic texts can be motivating because they are proof that the language is used for real-life purposes by real people” *Nuttall*(1996:172)

- Authentic material is easily available.
- It is highly motivating.
- A rich and rewarding reading environment with plenty of specific materials and devices that make reading enjoyable.
- Helps readers grow into real life readers.
- Learners are informed about what is happening in the world.
- Encourage reading for pleasure, likely to contain topics of interest.
- Reading is no longer viewed as a passive activity in which the reader strives to find all and only what the writer has written.
- Authentic materials provide a wide opportunity.
- Authentic material enables every learner reader to become an autonomous and critically aware reader of texts.
- Give scope for lot of illustrative pictorial materials.

- Supporting a more creative approach to learning/teaching.

Fluency in reading and comprehension of text may be successfully achieved only if we equip the learner / reader with reasonable amount of vocabulary.

VIII. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN AUTHENTIC AND NON-AUTHENTIC MATERIALS

A. Authentic Material:

- Authentic Material refers to any type of material that has not been produced in the class room.
- These are E-mail, voice messages, radio programs, video-clippings, applications etc.
- Through this the learner able to hear, read and convey his/her message.
- It makes them interesting and motivating.
- It is more useful in their day today life (real life situation).
- It is one of the most survival skills (social skill) that can be capable of understanding the context and interprets it.
- It is an opportunity to learn many new vocabulary items and difficult language structure.
- It makes the learner to collect some more authentic material to study and know the information.
- It also develops innovative skills among the learners and enhances their reasoning skills and critical thinking.

B. Non-Authentic Material:

- English Reader, Work Book, Work sheets, Test papers, Dictionaries, Grammar books are non-authentic materials.
- These non-authentic materials which are mostly used by teachers in the classroom.
- The English Readers are not updated one to cope up with day to day life. Learners will be bored with the same reading texts that are not attracting them.
- It will make them passive and become be a slow reader.

IX. CONCLUSION

The main objective of the present paper is to understand the effect of authentic materials are useful to promote good habits of reading among high school students. Authentic materials are useful for learning second language. However, the facilitator/teacher need creativity and knowledge for material adaptation. Regular teacher trainings, workshop, seminars on how the authentic materials are used will be useful for students to promote good habits of reading.

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Web Links:

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